

Vienna-Schwechat

VIE

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the airport of Vienna (VIE) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the airport area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the airport (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), wind frequency blowing from the airport in that WS, population living in the WS within 10 km from the airport, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the airport and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes.

The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

Vienna-VIE

Airport area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the airport within 5 and 10 km

Airport area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the airport within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gerwig, H., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., & Monge, S. (2025). Air quality around airports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2025/7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432053>).
[ETC HE Report 2025/7: Air quality around airports — Eionet Portal](#)

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NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	10.31	-37.95	3.42	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT32701	Background	48.15	16.48	14.27	-51.17	3.98	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT900KE	Background	48.16	16.48	17.45	-44.73	4.73	NW	16.91	31,636

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the airport (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	8.99		3.42	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	7.94		3.42	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT32701	Background	48.15	16.48	9.11	-47.72	3.98	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT900KE	Background	48.16	16.48	9.61		4.73	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT90LAA	Background	48.16	16.39	8.49		10.28	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT90A23	Traffic	48.20	16.43	10.28		10.64	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT9STAD	Background	48.23	16.46	10.80		11.94	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT30407	Background	48.23	16.64	8.65		12.16	N	10.96	7,285
Austria	AT9BELG	Background	48.17	16.36	10.20		13.01	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT90TAB	Traffic	48.22	16.38	10.61	-60.51	14.44	NW	16.91	31,636

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the airport (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Austria	AT31413	Background	48.08	16.33	9.10	-55.15	15.04	W	4.88	14,693
Austria	AT9GAUD	Background	48.19	16.34	9.40		15.10	NW	16.91	31,636

Pozzoli, L., Gerwig, H., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., & Monge, S. (2025). Air quality around airports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2025/7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432053>).
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Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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